

Evaluation of Airlines' Costs and Revenues in The Context of The Effects of Covid-19: An Application on Major Airlines

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Major Airlines Airlines' Costs Airlines' Revenues Airline Management</p> <p>Received: Oct., 20. 2023 Revised: Dec., 02. 2023 Accepted: Dec., 20. 2023</p>	<p>This study analysed the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on 58 airline companies' costs and revenues between 2017 and 2021. The trend analysis method was used to examine the change in revenues and expenses, with 2017 as the base year. The analysis revealed that airline company revenues were stable until March 2020, and efforts were made to maintain a balance between income and expenses. Out of the 58 airlines analysed, Lion Tra experienced the most significant decrease in revenue ratio, followed by Norwegian Air and Thai Airways. The Covid-19 outbreak had a significant impact on airline operator expenses. Among the airlines, Spicejet had the highest proportional increase in expenses, followed by Wizz Air and Air Asia.</p>

1. Introduction

Air transportation is a crucial sector that enhances global connectivity, supports economic development, and facilitates interaction worldwide. The realization of these benefits, and others expected from the aviation sector, is highly dependent on the success of airline businesses. The success of airline businesses is closely linked to their revenues and expenses, which are affected by intense competition and low profit margins. ICAO (2007) has classified the costs of airline operations into two groups. The two types of operating costs are direct and indirect. Direct operating costs consist of flight operating costs, aircraft maintenance costs, and depreciation costs. Flight operating costs include costs for flight personnel, fuel and oil, insurance, and aircraft and flight personnel leasing. Indirect Operating Costs comprise expenses related to airport and air navigation services usage, station expenses, passenger services expenses, ticketing, sales, promotion expenses, administrative expenses, general, and other expenses. Analysis of airline company revenues reveals that they generate ancillary revenues in addition to revenues from direct ticket sales to passengers. Ancillary revenues in the aviation industry include À la carte sales revenues, commission-based revenues, revenues from frequent flyer programs, and advertising revenues (Çetiner et al., 2019; O'Connell et al., 2013).

The COVID-19 pandemic, which originated in China and impacted the entire world, caused a global crisis and had a significant impact on air transportation (Kim and Sohn, 2022). Initially, countries suspended all flight activities with China and subsequently with other countries affected by the virus. As of July 2020, airline companies have conducted a very limited number of domestic and international passenger transportation

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activities worldwide. In these flight activities, occupancy rates are currently very low (Karakavuz, 2020). This has resulted in significant revenue losses for airline companies.

2. Literature Review

Airline transportation is a broad research field that encompasses operational processes, environmental impacts, aviation safety and security, as well as sector-specific issues. Furthermore, numerous studies have been conducted on the costs and revenues of airline companies, which are the most significant actors in the industry (Gillen & Morrison, 2003; Kiraci, 2019; Kiraci & Aydin, 2018; Post, 2010; Vinod, 2022; Warnock-Smith et al., 2017). Understanding airline revenues and expenses is crucial for assessing competition and sustainability in the sector. Akbaba (2022) conducted a study to determine the costs incurred by airline companies due to irregular flights and their impact on the cost structure of these companies. The research revealed that irregular operations, such as delayed, cancelled, and diverted flights, affect the fixed cost structure of airline operations. Köse (2020) conducted a study on the cost systems of business class and economy class in airline businesses. The traditional cost system and activity-based cost system were compared. The study found that the activity-based cost system is a strategic management system that can increase economic profitability and expand market shares within the sector. Çetiner et al. (2019) conducted a study on ancillary revenues and the preferences of managers and passengers in different types of airline business models. In a survey study conducted with 160 airline managers from 17 different international airlines and 188 airline passengers from 24 different countries, it was found that airline managers and passengers prefer different ancillary revenue generation methods in different airline business models. Yükü and Fidancı (2018) suggested ways to improve cost calculations for more accurate pricing in airline passenger transportation. In this context, it has been suggested that fuel and similar costs are directly related to the weight of the passenger. Therefore, using weight as a factor in calculating the cost of passengers can provide airlines with more accurate cost calculations and pricing. Kiracı (2020) conducted research on the financial variables affecting the profitability of low-cost airlines from 2004-20. A systematic literature review on revenue management for passenger airlines was conducted by Ammirato et al. (2020). Dai et al. (2018) focused on problems such as customer cancellations and reservation non-use, examining two different demand models on airline revenue management system. Lin and Hong (2020) presented a relational network data envelopment analysis DEA model to evaluate the cost efficiency, cost effectiveness, and service effectiveness of airlines. The study analysed eight airline businesses in Taiwan and China and found that, in general, service efficiency was better than cost efficiency. The authors also concluded that Chinese enterprises were significantly more cost efficient and cost effective than Taiwanese companies. Gudmundsson et al. (2020) conducted a study on the effects of post-expenditure cost structure in horizontal mergers and acquisitions. In this context, the authors empirically measured the effects of cost structure to inform competition policy regarding mergers and acquisitions in the airline industry. The study found that horizontal mergers and acquisitions involving unprofitable businesses significantly reduce variable costs and subsequently increase fixed costs. Swidan and Merkert (2019) conducted a study on the cost impact of operational hedging and its relationship with financial hedging among a sample of 80 global airlines. The study revealed that operational hedging, based on aircraft engine commonality, significantly reduces operating costs. However, it is not an effective standalone strategy for managing jet fuel risk. Recent literature has examined the cost and revenue structure of airlines (Bourjade & Muller-Vibes, 2023; Ding et al., 2023; Jaroenjitrkam et al., 2023; Lesgourgues & Malavolti, 2023; Liu et al., 2023; Ng et al., 2023; Sugishita et al., 2024). However, no comprehensive study has yet included the Covid-19 effect. Therefore, this study aims to contribute to the literature.

3. Methodology

The trend analysis method, also referred to as the trend percentages method, is a technique used to analyse enterprise performance indicators. This analysis involves using statistical tests to determine whether there is a significant increase or decrease (trend) in the measured values of a growth rate over time. To maximise the benefits of trend analysis, it is recommended to use data that covers the longest possible period. In trend analysis, changes in the analysed indicator are measured by year. The year considered as the beginning is known as the 'base year' and the value of the relevant year is set to 100. The percentage change of the values in other years compared to the base year is then calculated. This method allows for the determination of increases and decreases in data over the years, revealing the performance of enterprises (Akcanlı et al., 2013).

$$\text{Trend Percentage} = \frac{\text{Current year value of account figures (x year)}}{\text{Base year value}} \times 100$$

This study analyses the data of 58 major airline companies that transport passengers worldwide between 2017 and 2021, using 2017 as the base year.

4. Results

Covid-19 has been declared a global pandemic by the World Health Organisation. In order to prevent the pandemic from spreading worldwide and to reduce its impact, countries closed their borders and imposed travel restrictions. During this period, the airline industry experienced extraordinary revenue losses and financial deterioration in cash flow. To understand the impact of the Covid-19 outbreak on an airline business, it is useful to mention a number of decisions taken by Delta Airlines in this process. First and foremost, Delta Airlines reduced capacity to cope with the sudden drop in demand caused by the pandemic. Specifically, in 2020, it reduced system capacity by approximately 50%, international capacity by approximately 65% and domestic capacity by approximately 45% compared to the previous year. To balance system capacity in the March 2021 quarter due to reduced demand and capacity, the airline retired 227 aircraft in 2020 and temporarily parked approximately 125 aircraft at 31 December 2020. In response to the revenue decline, cost savings were focused on expense management. To reduce personnel costs, most employees were granted voluntary unpaid leave of between 30 days and 12 months. In addition, early retirement and voluntary separation programmes were implemented to reduce personnel costs. Aircraft orders were reallocated to future deliveries and aircraft replacements were postponed. Share buybacks and dividends were suspended indefinitely (Delta Air Lines, 2020).

This study, conducted to examine the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on airline companies, examined the rate of change in costs and revenues of 58 airlines before and after the Covid-19 pandemic (2017-2021).

Table 1: Airline net sales or revenues between 2017 and 2021 (Base year 2017)

AIRLINE	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
LION TRA	100	108.05	108.22	25.06	7.15
NORWEGIAN AIR	100	120.16	121.30	25.42	14.67
THAI AIRWAYS	100	104.40	103.12	26.52	11.56
EL AL ISRAEL AIRLINE	100	102.04	104.78	30.05	41.16
HAWAIIAN	100	105.26	105.07	31.34	59.23
FINNAIR	100	107.62	111.72	31.95	32.53
CROATIA AIRLINES	100	100.82	96.89	32.42	44.55
AIR CANADA	100	104.05	109.74	33.77	38.84
IAG	100	103.60	102.85	33.89	36.66
CEBU AIR	100	104.05	122.60	34.98	23.75
GARUDA INDONESIA	100	99.21	108.56	35.08	31.98
GOL LINHAS AEREAS	100	80.98	100.03	35.49	42.38
JEJU AIR	100	127.49	130.90	35.98	26.79
AEGEAN AIRLINES	100	102.68	107.51	36.43	59.64
DEUTSCHE LUFTHANSA	100	98.24	94.83	37.79	47.09
GRUPO AEROMEXICO	100	104.49	101.05	38.24	66.12
LATAM AIRLINES	100	91.13	98.18	39.69	48.48
AMERICAN AIRLINES	100	105.53	108.44	41.08	70.80
PEGASUS	100	80.47	124.12	41.30	82.31
DELTA AIR LINES	100	107.74	113.97	41.45	72.49
JETBLUE AIRWAYS	100	109.17	115.38	42.15	86.06
TUI AG	100	102.71	94.60	42.41	25.44
FRANCE - KLM	100	100.28	97.68	42.55	55.33
SOUTHWEST AIRLINES	100	103.75	105.94	42.74	74.58
AEROFLOT-ROSSIY	100	96.18	110.47	43.04	72.70
AZUL	100	88.20	112.08	43.44	77.22
ALASKA AIR	100	104.17	110.69	44.95	77.85
KENYA AIRWAYS	100	108.62	118.42	46.73	61.18
HAINAN AIRLINES	100	108.36	110.79	47.01	57.60

VIETNAM AIRLINES	100	113.78	116.02	47.92	33.59
CATHAY PACIFIC AIR	100	113.81	109.77	48.71	47.19
AIR ARABIA	100	110.24	127.27	49.50	84.89
AIR CHINA	100	105.64	100.67	53.68	60.98
TURK HAVA YOLLARI	100	78.79	113.31	54.70	98.40
CHINA EASTERN	100	107.76	108.24	54.90	66.47
EVA AIRWAYS	100	107.46	106.51	55.82	69.00
ASIANA AIRLINES	100	116.36	105.42	59.47	68.13
KOREAN AIR LINES	100	108.61	98.85	59.80	72.89
EASYJET	100	116.22	119.68	60.44	30.76
PAKISTAN INTL AIR	100	96.10	106.36	60.54	53.36
SHANDONG AIRLINES	100	109.05	105.62	61.21	77.04
ALLEGIAN	100	110.88	122.42	65.84	113.57
SKYWEST	100	100.54	92.75	66.38	84.68
SPIRIT AIR	100	125.51	144.68	68.36	122.02
CHINA SOUTHERN	100	107.65	110.70	69.37	80.70
THOMAS COOK (INDIA)	100	117.17	68.63	69.75	8.13
CHINA AIRLINES	100	106.83	103.68	75.69	96.62
QANTAS AIRWAYS	100	95.26	95.06	79.02	31.96
SPRING AIRLINES	100	114.51	123.72	81.84	100.43
AIR NEW ZEALAND	100	97.40	99.43	87.18	48.49
SINGAPORE AIRLINES	100	104.42	107.17	106.20	25.87
JAPAN AIRLINES	100	104.69	117.33	112.09	37.06
ANA HOLDINGS	100	108.97	118.57	114.50	40.97
IAG HOLDINGS	100	81.15	74.13	114.89	97.87
RYANAIR	100	104.89	107.26	126.45	24.52
AIR ASIA	100	109.89	155.54	165.18	174.58
SPICEJET	100	112.70	131.50	175.23	73.35
WIZZ AIR	100	129.25	146.44	185.16	52.95

Table 1 shows the results of the trend analysis of the revenues of 58 airlines before (2017-2019) and after (2020-2021) Covid-19. The analysis was performed using 2017 as the base year. In this context, significant differences were found in the airlines' revenues between the pre- and post-pandemic periods. It can be assumed that most of the airlines studied increased their revenues in 2017 and 2018, and that this positive trend continued until 2019. However, with the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, significant economic difficulties emerged across the sector and a significant decline in airline company revenues was observed. The Covid-19 pandemic led to the introduction of international flight restrictions from March 2020, resulting in a significant reduction in demand for air travel. This led to a significant decline in airline revenues. Restrictions on passenger traffic have led airlines to review their business strategies and seek alternative sources of revenue.

Of the 58 airlines analysed, Lion Tra was identified as the airline with the most dramatic decline, with its revenue rate falling from 108.22 in 2019 to 25.06 in 2020. Similarly, Norwegian Air's revenue ratio will fall from 121.30 to 25.42, making it the second airline to experience a significant decline due to the impact of the pandemic. Thai Airways, on the other hand, is the third most affected airline, with its revenue ratio falling from 103.12 to 26.52 in 2020.

Among the 58 airlines studied, Wizz Air shows a remarkable performance by increasing its revenue ratio from 146.44 in 2019 to 185.16 in 2020, turning the pandemic period into an opportunity and proportionally increasing its revenue the most. This success reflects the effectiveness and adaptability of Wizz Air's strategies to deal with the crisis. Spicejet increased its revenue ratio from 131.50 in 2019 to 175.53 in 2020, becoming the second airline to proportionally increase its revenue during the pandemic period. Air Asia ranked third, increasing its revenue ratio from 155.54 in 2019 to 165.18 in 2020. Air Asia also increases its revenue proportionally in 2021, with a revenue ratio of 174.58.

During the Covid 19 period, Turkish Airlines has turned to compensating for revenue losses by increasing its cargo activities to offset the decline in passenger demand. During this period, THY was positioned as the second airline with the most flights in Europe (Hopancı, B.-Akdeniz H.-Şahin, O.). This shows that THY has adapted to the crisis period by effectively using its extensive flight network and its potential in cargo transport. Pegasus, on the other hand, tried to optimise its revenue losses by operating domestic flights despite the restrictions and benefiting from government support (Pegasus, 2020, "November 2020 Comparative Traffic

Data"). These strategic choices enabled Pegasus to maintain its operational flexibility and demonstrate sustainable performance during the crisis period.

Table 2: Total operating costs of airlines between 2017 and 2021 (base year 2017).

AIRLINE	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
SPICEJET	100	111.14	142.07	192.86	101.81
WIZZ AIR	100	130.34	151.25	192.72	99.73
AIR ASIA	100	116.48	162.42	177.84	185.70
RYANAIR	100	104.56	121.01	142.56	49.87
HAINAN AIRLINES	100	114.73	117.56	127.93	83.57
ANA HOLDINGS	100	108.86	118.86	120.94	73.14
JAPAN AIRLINES	100	105.41	119.18	120.04	77.81
SPIRIT AIR	100	128.17	147.69	116.78	163.33
IAG HOLDINGS	100	92.08	80.16	109.64	92.86
SINGAPORE AIRLINES	100	101.52	104.64	105.44	43.27
AIR NEW ZEALAND	100	97.92	105.32	99.17	61.83
SPRING AIRLINES	100	116.67	123.40	98.24	118.31
ALLEGiant	100	114.71	118.98	90.00	131.55
QANTAS AIRWAYS	100	94.59	96.69	89.23	50.84
SKYWEST	100	97.56	86.57	83.94	98.57
GARUDA INDONESIA	100	100.74	101.51	83.44	69.07
EASYJET	100	113.66	121.29	82.52	56.69
JETBLUE AIRWAYS	100	114.98	120.65	82.16	115.26
SHANDONG AIRLINES	100	110.72	106.50	82.01	93.15
CHINA SOUTHERN	100	109.33	110.82	81.93	93.88
ALASKA AIR	100	113.93	117.30	80.59	97.97
SOUTHWEST AIRLINES	100	106.39	110.28	79.59	96.38
CEBU AIR	100	110.63	122.62	78.85	68.98
CHINA AIRLINES	100	110.56	108.16	78.70	91.37
JEJU AIR	100	130.52	149.18	78.06	64.42
AMERICAN AIRLINES	100	109.83	112.42	76.77	94.60
AZUL	100	93.52	107.49	75.04	95.84
CHINA EASTERN	100	108.23	108.47	75.01	88.14
DELTA AIR LINES	100	112.49	115.71	72.53	93.33
AIR CHINA	100	108.19	102.54	72.19	86.02
THOMAS COOK (INDIA)	100	117.83	70.31	72.01	13.56
ASIANA AIRLINES	100	121.27	117.33	66.68	69.80
FRANCE - KLM	100	98.43	97.02	66.55	64.27
KENYA AIRWAYS	100	109.06	115.54	65.86	68.41
KOREAN AIR LINES	100	111.97	105.00	63.92	66.68
TURK HAVA YOLLARI	100	77.19	116.94	63.83	93.43
VIETNAM AIRLINES	100	112.76	116.54	63.53	51.31
GRUPO AEROMEXICO	100	106.50	100.69	63.41	76.65
LATAM AIRLINES	100	90.47	96.04	63.20	62.88
AEROFLOT-ROSSIY	100	100.95	111.82	62.70	81.56
AIR ARABIA	100	111.44	117.45	62.35	77.70
AIR CANADA	100	106.41	109.69	61.59	62.94
AEGEAN AIRLINES	100	104.16	107.17	61.42	71.94
CATHAY PACIFIC AIR	100	113.42	110.93	60.61	52.60
PEGASUS	100	79.12	109.07	60.59	93.72
IAG	100	103.18	103.24	60.19	56.95
HAWAIIAN	100	113.68	114.46	59.78	90.97
DEUTSCHE LUFTHANSA	100	99.56	99.54	59.60	60.18
EVA AIRWAYS	100	107.89	106.63	59.50	65.60
FINNAIR	100	107.91	111.98	58.56	54.49
PAKISTAN INTL AIR	100	96.41	88.23	58.47	53.58
TUI AG	100	103.55	96.41	56.81	36.40
CROATIA AIRLINES	100	99.53	95.89	55.18	61.95
GOL LINHAS AEREAS	100	85.60	95.93	51.49	72.08
THAI AIRWAYS	100	111.15	114.08	49.49	22.28
EL AL ISRAEL AIRLINE	100	105.77	106.56	48.90	56.05
NORWEGIAN AIR	100	124.50	114.69	47.39	23.51
LION TRA	100	109.17	109.50	29.19	11.23

Table 2 shows the results of the trend analysis of the expenses of 58 airlines before (2017-2019) and after (2020-2021) Covid-19. As can be seen, the airlines' expenses are different before and after the pandemic. Although the airlines' revenues were high before Covid-19, it can be seen that their expenses were high in the same direction. In 2021, when airlines started to operate their flights normally, it can be seen that most airlines have increased their revenues and their expenses have also increased. Since there is no increase in the number of flights of some companies, it is seen that they cannot increase their revenue but their expenses are also low.

Spicejet has been identified as the airline that has proportionally increased its expenses the most, increasing its expense ratio from 142.07 in 2019 to 192.86 in 2020 over the period studied. After Spicejet, Wizz Air increased its expense ratio from 151.25 in 2019 to 192.72 in 2020, making it the second airline with the highest increase. Similarly, Air Asia was among the airlines with the highest expenses, increasing its expense ratio from 162.42 in 2019 to 177.84 in 2020.

Table 1 shows that Lion Tra is the airline with the highest proportional decrease in revenue. However, Lion Tra's data in Table 2 shows that it is the airline with the lowest expenses in 2020. This situation indicates that Lion Tra could not sufficiently continue its activities after Covid 19 and suffered a lot of financial losses. Norwegian Airline is the 2nd airline that proportionally decreased its expenses, reducing its expenses from 114.69 units in 2019 to 47.39 units in 2020. The 3rd airline to reduce its expenses proportionally is El Al Israel Airline. It will reduce its expenses from 106.56 units in 2019 to 48.90 units in 2020. (Delta Air Lines Inc. 2020)

5. Discussions and Conclusion

Aviation is a sector that has historically faced various challenges and has been directly exposed to crises. These challenges have come in the form of various threats to airlines, economic disruptions and major terrorist incidents in recent years. Examples include the 1973 oil crisis, the Gulf War, the Asian economic crisis, the September 11 attacks, the SARS crisis and most recently the Covid-19 outbreak. The Covid-19 crisis, which occurred at the end of 2009, had a profound impact on the air transport sector. In such crises, the decline in demand for passenger and cargo transport has had a significant impact on the financial situation of air carriers, leading to significant changes in the sector. The main objective of this study is to analyse the revenues and expenses of 58 major airlines using a trend analysis methodology, taking into account the period before and after Covid-19. This analysis is crucial to understand the changes in the sector, the impact of crises and the changes in airline performance indicators. The trend analysis will provide valuable information to identify strengths and weaknesses in the sector, to make strategic plans and to be better prepared for future uncertainties.

With 2017 as the base year, the results of the analysis show that until March 2020, the airlines were operating normally, trying to balance their revenues and expenses. However, as a result of the restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic, the reduction in the number of flights and the decrease in in-flight and out-of-flight revenues caused serious financial losses. In 2021, most airlines began a rapid recovery process, driven by strong domestic markets. This indicates the positive impact of increased domestic demand and the industry's recovery efforts. However, the sustainability of this recovery and the future of the sector should be closely monitored due to various uncertainties. Following this study, a more detailed analysis can be carried out to understand the impact of the Covid-19 outbreak on the costs of the airlines carrying the largest number of international passengers. In this context, the financial difficulties caused by the decline in passenger demand, operational constraints and travel restrictions caused by the pandemic can be examined and the impact on the cost structures of these airlines can be studied in detail.

Conflicts of Interest

With regard to the publication of this paper, the authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

References

- Akbaba, A. (2022). Düzensiz operasyonların havayolu ücret politikalarına ve gelir yönetimine etkisi üzerine modelleme. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 14(4), 2833-2847.
- Akcanlı, F., Soba, M., & Kestane, A. (2013). İmkb'ye kote edilmiş havayolu taşımacılığı sektöründe trend analizine ilişkin örnek bir uygulama. *Uşak Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 6(3), 191- 207.
- Ammirato, S., Felicetti, A. M., Linzalone, R., Volpentesta, A. P., & Schiuma, G. (2020). A systematic literature review of revenue management in passenger transportation. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 24(2), 223-242.
- Bourjade, S., & Muller-Vibes, C. (2023). Optimal leasing and airlines' cost efficiency: A stochastic frontier analysis. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 176, 103804. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRA.2023.103804>
- Çetiner, E. M., Güneş, M. F., & Peker, A. E. (2019). Havayolu şirketlerinde yan gelir: Havayolu yöneticilerinin ve yolcu tercihlerinin karşılaştırılması. *Ekonomi İşletme ve Maliye Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 1(2), 135-155.
- Dai, J., Kleywegt, A. J., & Xiao, Y. (2019). Network revenue management with cancellations and No-Shows. *Production and Operations Management*, 28(2), 292-318.
- Delta Airlines (2020). Delta-Air-Lines-Announces-December-Quarter-and-Full-Year-2020-Results.
- Ding, C., Chen, X., Wu, W., Wei, W., & Xin, Z. (2023). Game-theoretic analysis of the impact of crew overnight hotel cost on airlines' fleet assignment and crew pairing. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 113, 102491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JAIRTRAMAN.2023.102491>
- Gillen, D., & Morrison, W. (2003). Bundling, integration and the delivered price of air travel: Are low-cost carriers' full-service competitors? *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 9(1), 15-23. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315091617-21>
- Gudmundsson, S. V., Merkert, R., & Redondi, R. (2020). Cost structure effects of horizontal airline mergers and acquisitions. *Transport Policy*, 99, 136-144.
- ICAO, (2007). Outlook for air transport to the year 2025. Montreal: ICAO Press.
- Jaroenjitrkam, A., Kotcharin, S., & Maneenop, S. (2023). Corporate resilience to the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence from the airline industry. *The Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics*, 39(4), 26-36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AJSL.2023.10.003>
- Karakavuz, H. (2020). Covid-19'un Türk havayolu işletmeleri üzerindeki etkilerine ilişkin bir swot analizi. *Electronic Turkish Studies*, 15(8).
- Kim, M., & Sohn, J. (2022). Passenger, airline, and policy responses to the COVID-19 crisis: The case of South Korea. *Journal of air transport management*, 98, 102144.
- Kiraci, K. (2019). Determinants of financial risk: An empirical application on low-cost carriers. *Scientific Annals of Economics and Business*, 66(3). <https://doi.org/10.2478/saeb-2019-0025>
- Kiraci, K. (2020). The factors determining the profitability of low-cost airlines, *Romanian Statistical Review*, 1, pp. 41-53.
- Kiraci, K., & Aydın, N. (2018). Factors that determine the capital structure: An empirical study on low-cost airlines. *Scientific Annals of Economics and Business*, 65(3). <https://doi.org/10.2478/saeb-2018-0018>
- Köse, Y. (2020). Havayolu sektöründe geleneksel ve faaliyet tabanlı maliyetleme uygulamalarının karşılaştırılması: Analitik bir inceleme. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Management Inquiries*, 4(Özel Sayı 1), 227-236.
- Lesgourgues, A., & Malavolti, E. (2023). Social cost of airline delays: Assessment by the use of revenue management data. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 170, 103613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRA.2023.103613>
- Lin, Y. H., & Hong, C. F. (2020). Efficiency and effectiveness of airline companies in Taiwan and Mainland China. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 25(1), 13-22.
- Liu, D., Zhang, J., & Yu, M. M. (2023). Decomposing airline profit inefficiency in NDEA through the non-competitive Nerlovian profit inefficiency model. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 107, 102350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JAIRTRAMAN.2022.102350>
- Ng, K. T., Fu, X., Lee, J., Yamaguchi, K., & Zhu, C. (2023). The Effects of Bankruptcy on Airline Yield and Frequency: The case of the duopolistic domestic market in Japan. *Transport Policy*, 142, 28-36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRANPOL.2023.07.024>
- O'Connell, J. F., & Warnock-Smith, D. (2013). An investigation into traveler preferences and acceptance levels of airline ancillary revenues. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 33, 12-21.

- Post, D. (2010). Variable opaque products in the airline industry: A tool to fill the gaps and increase revenues. *Journal of Revenue and Pricing Management*, 9(4), 292–299. <https://doi.org/10.1057/RPM.2010.13/FIGURES/1>
- Sugishita, K., Mizutani, H., & Hanaoka, S. (2024). Disruption and recovery of the US domestic airline networks during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 114, 102504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JAIRTRAMAN.2023.102504>
- Swidan, H., & Merkert, R. (2019). The relative effect of operational hedging on airline operating costs. *Transport Policy*, 80, 70-77.
- Vinod, B. (2022). Airline revenue planning and the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Tourism Futures*, 8(2), 245–253. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JTF-02-2021-0055/FULL/PDF>
- Warnock-Smith, D., O’Connell, J. F., & Maleki, M. (2017). An analysis of ongoing trends in airline ancillary revenues. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 64, 42–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JAIRTRAMAN.2017.06.023>
- Yükçü, S.& Fidancı, N. (2018). Havayolu işletmeciliğinde maliyet ve fiyatlandırma önerileri. *Journal of Accounting and Taxation Studies*, 394-407.

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